

EU-FarmBook

BEGINNER'S GUIDE

EU-FarmBook Platform

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01

Preface

Agriculture and forestry are sectors of unique importance at an economic, social, and environmental level. However, both activities face unprecedented challenges

While meeting growing population's needs, agriculture and forestry must preserve biodiversity, tackle climate change effects, and minimize natural resource use. Efficiency is crucial for agriculture and forestry to boost productivity while reducing their environmental footprint.

The EU introduced directives emphasizing the need for agriculture and forestry to confront outlined challenges. This includes the new Common Agricultural Policy, the Green Deal or the Farm to Fork, Biodiversity and Forestry strategies. On these directives, the EU acknowledges that research and innovation are crucial elements in addressing these challenges. It is then clear that agriculture and forestry must become more intensive in research and innovation.

This entails not only developing research and innovation solutions, but also ensure their applicability.

The EU supports the development of research and innovation solutions through programs like H2020, Horizon Europe, or Operational Groups, involving various actors from Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).

However, for these solutions to be effective, they must be readily available and easily applicable, empowering farmers, foresters and advisors to tackle present and future challenges efficiently. **EU-FarmBook was born from this approach. EU-FarmBook is an online platform, that aspires to be the point of reference for farmers, foresters and advisors .**

02

EU-FarmBook Platform

EU-FarmBook is an under-development online platform that gathers and provides practice-oriented materials from the domain of agriculture and forestry.

These materials derive from research and innovation projects funded by the EU (Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe Framework Programmes or EIP-AGRI Operational Groups), or from national and/or regional knowledge reservoirs.

EU-FarmBook contributes to overcoming current challenges inherent in agriculture and forestry: fostering the transposition of research and innovation solutions to practice, ensuring that research and innovation solutions are readily available and connecting actors of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) at national, regional, and EU levels.

EU-FarmBook is being developed by building upon the work already done in the EURAKNOS and EUREKA Horizon 2020 projects (the predecessors of the EU-FarmBook) both at the technical and conceptual level.

*EU-FarmBook
aspires to be the
point of reference
for farmers,
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03

Practice-Oriented Materials

*A **practice-oriented material or knowledge object** refers to documents, videos, presentations, or other items developed under research and innovation projects funded by the EU (Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe Framework Programmes or EIP-AGRI Operational Groups) or available at national and/or regional knowledge reservoirs.*

A practice-oriented material should address needs of farmers, foresters, and advisors, and be in non-technical and/or non-political language

Practice-oriented materials or knowledge objects are made available in a broad range of formats to cater for the needs and preferences of various types of users. Practice-oriented materials are grouped into seven broad categories: text documents,

videos, presentations, audios, images, applications, and datasets. These categories, together with a variety of other information about practice-oriented materials, make it easier to provide different users with the kind of results they are looking for.

TEXT DOCUMENTS

VIDEOS

PRESENTATIONS

AUDIOS

APPLICATIONS

DATASETS

IMAGES

04 Knowledge Flows

EU-FarmBook Contributors

*EU-FarmBook is a platform that **gathers** practice-oriented materials*

Practice-oriented materials or knowledge objects can be made available to the EU-FarmBook platform by an authorized contributor - that can be either a partner or coordinator of a research and innovation project funded by the EU or a manager of a national and/or regional knowledge reservoir). Practice-oriented materials or knowledge objects can be provided by using the EU-FarmBook Upload Form or the Application Programming Interface (a programmatic way of providing materials for the technically literate).

06

EU-FarmBook Users

EU-FarmBook is a platform that provides practice-oriented materials

FARMERS

FORESTERS

ADVISORS

STUDENTS

EDUCATORS

The EU-FarmBook platform aims to reach a large audience constituting the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) community in the EU. This audience is primarily made up of people involved in forestry and agriculture, who will have the opportunity to interact with the EU-FarmBook platform either by having the role of contributors of practice-oriented materials or users interested in finding and accessing information and solutions of relevance to their everyday practice or other activities.

Under this lens, there is a range of platform users to consider. The main user group targeted by the EU-FarmBook platform are farmers, foresters, advisors, students, and educators.

Practice-Oriented Materials: Metadata

Having a practice-oriented material or knowledge object described with the correct metadata is very important as it can enable successful searches in the EU-FarmBook platform. Examples of metadata include the creator, the title, keywords, or subject labels letting the user know the what the material is about. It is of great importance for metadata to be easily read and interpreted both by humans and computers to easily categorise practice-oriented materials and make them easier to find and collect.

The metadata used for practice-oriented materials description in the EU-FarmBook platform has been considered as the minimum set of information identified as a must have for an adequate description. All our metadata have been defined by using existing and well-known ontologies and vocabularies

Title

Title assigned to the practice-oriented material by its creator. In the case of materials such as datasets or software applications, it represents the name of the dataset or software application (E.g. Yield Estimation Calculator).

Description

A concise textual description detailing the content of the practice-oriented material. For documents, this description could serve as the abstract of the document.

Keywords

A collection of keywords or keyphrases associated with the practice-oriented material. Keywords should accurately reflect the information and content of the material, facilitating search and discoverability for platform users.

Creator(s)

Practice-oriented materials are the outcome of work within a project and are crafted by one or more individuals. These individuals are the creators of the material.

Language(s)

Research and innovation projects disseminate their findings (practice-oriented materials) not only in English but also in other languages. Information regarding the language(s) in which a material is available is crucial for addressing multilingual aspects.

Date of Completion

This denotes the date (preferably in DD/MM/YYYY format) indicating the precise time of the creation of the practice-oriented material. This information is vital considering the pace at which results are generated and how quickly they become outdated.

Intended Purpose

Not all practice-oriented materials are created to serve the same purpose. Making the purpose of a material known can help identify objects of interest and usefulness to the EU-FarmBook platform users.

Geographic Location(s)

Providing information on the location(s) related to the content of a practice-oriented material aids users of the platform in finding information relevant to their location. This allows users to access information and content pertinent to their area.

URL

This metadata property is used to capture the link to the source of the practice-oriented material (the database or web-based inventory of the project that created the material).

Category

The category to which the practice-oriented material belongs (such as text documents, videos, presentations, audios, images, applications, and datasets).

Type

The practice-oriented materials on the platform fall into various categories, each associated with different types based on the content/information provided and the format in which it is available. Specific types of materials exist for each category.

Subject

This represents the subject (topic) of the practice-oriented material. To enable the capture of subjects in as detailed a manner as possible, subjects are defined at two levels of detail.

License

It may be the case that a practice-oriented material has been assigned a license by its creator(s) specifying the conditions and terms of (re-) use.

Format

Practice-oriented material can be available in a variety of file formats. Formats are heavily related to the category of the material. For example, the format of a document differs from that of a video (E.g. csv, pdf, png, mpg, etc.).

File Size

This metadata property relates to the size of the digital file in which the practice-oriented material becomes available (E.g. KBs, MBs).

Project Name

The full name of the research and innovation project that is the source of the practice-oriented material (the project in which the material has been created).

Project Acronym

The acronym (or short name) of the research and innovation project in which the practice-oriented material has been created.

Project URL

The URL of the official website of the research and innovation project in which the practice-oriented material has been created. The link to the webpage of the project on CORDIS (www.cordis.europa.eu) can be used.

Practice-Oriented Materials: Upload

EU-FarmBook Upload Form

The EU-FarmBook Platform's Upload Form will enable people working in various projects to upload individual practice-oriented materials. It provides an easy to comprehend and user-friendly interface which guiding contributors through the upload process. A user must log in to upload and have the role of the contributor assigned by (for example) the coordinator of a project or other authorized user of the platform.

EU-FarmBook Application Programming Interface

As opposed to the EU-FarmBook Platform's Upload Form aimed to be used for the upload of (relatively) small numbers of practice-oriented materials, the EU-FarmBook Platform's API (Application Programming Interface) allows for large-scale programmatic uploads.

09

EU-FarmBook Platform Features

OPEN ACCESS

POWERFUL SEARCH ENGINE

FREE

EASY UPLOAD PROCESS

TRUSTWORTHY

DEDICATED SUPPORT CENTER

AUTOMATIC TRANSLATION

PROTECTS AUTHORS

Features of EU-FarmBook	Access without registration	Access with registration
Access contributions	✓	✓
Download contributions	✓	✓
Access to feedback on contributions	—	✓
Join the community and engage with peers IN FUTURE	—	✓
Search for relevant content and contributions	✓	✓
Enhanced search	—	✓
Receive customised content	—	✓
Engage with experts IN FUTURE	—	✓

What to expect regarding multilingual support?

2024: You have the capability to upload practice-oriented materials in multiple EU languages.

2025: The platform interface will be accessible in all EU languages.

2026: Content from selected practice-oriented materials will be automatically translated into three languages and English.

2027: Content from selected practice-oriented materials will be automatically translated into more than three languages and English.

10

Other Useful Resources

This guide forms part of the documentation expected to be released throughout the EU-FarmBook project's lifetime to better guide and support the people involved in research and innovation projects funded by the EU, national and/or regional knowledge reservoirs, or any member of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), about the EU-FarmBook Platform.

Other resources to be considered are the EU-FarmBook Platform's **User Manual**, **Explanation Videos**, and the **Metadata Guide**.

Date of publication:

May 2024

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